

SODIUM REMOVAL CAPACITY BY EXOPOLYSACCHARIDE OF *RHIZOBIUM RADIOBACTER* 36 TO MITIGATE SALT STRESS

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Exopolysaccharides (EPS) play a crucial role in preserving genetic resources in salt-affected soils by enhancing soil structure and stability (Rasulov et al., 2020). These high-molecular-weight polymers, secreted by soil microorganisms, bind soil particles together, forming aggregates that improve porosity and water retention. In saline conditions, EPS contribute to the formation of biofilms, which protect microbial communities from environmental stresses like high salt concentrations. By creating a more hospitable microenvironment, EPS allow beneficial microbes to thrive, thus supporting a biodiverse microbial community essential for soil health and plant growth. In addition, EPS help in nutrient cycling and facilitate the growth of salt-tolerant plants by reducing the toxicity of sodium ions in the soil (Rasulov et al., 2020). Through ion sequestration, EPS limit the availability of toxic ions, which can otherwise hinder plant and microbial growth. The preserved microbial diversity, fostered by EPS in these saline soils, aids in the maintenance of genetic resources, as different microbial species possess genes essential for stress tolerance, nutrient solubilization, and plant growth promotion. This microbial gene pool is critical for the adaptive resilience of soil ecosystems, particularly in salt-affected areas, making EPS vital for sustaining soil biodiversity and agricultural productivity under saline conditions.

In the present study, it was aimed to investigate the sodium removal capabilities of EPS by *Rhizobium radiobacter* 36.

Bacteria of the *Rhizobium* genus are characterized by the synthesis of exopolysaccharides (EPS), which play a crucial role in cell defense against abiotic stress, such as salinity, drought, and heavy metal exposure (Das et al., 2019; Rasulov et al., 2020). These polysaccharides are pivotal in the symbiotic relationship between rhizobia and leguminous plants, facilitating the formation of root nodules where nitrogen fixation occurs (Marczak et al., 2017; Castellani et al., 2021; Acosta-Jurado et al., 2021).

One of the important properties of EPS in mitigation of the salt stress is Na⁺ removal capacity of EPS (Rasulov et al., 2020). This case was also observed in current research. While cultivating *R. radiobacter* 36 in presence of different concentrations of NaCl, EPS actively removed Na⁺ cations from the medium. The EPS of *R. radiobacter* 36 absorbed different amounts of Na⁺ ions from model solutions of NaCl. Maximal Na⁺ removal was observed when it was mixed with 2.0 % NaCl. In this variant the EPS removed. 2.149 g Na⁺/100 g EPS. Further increasing of NaCl concentration (2.5% Na⁺ removal was almost the same as in 2.0% NaCl solution. Na⁺ -removal analysis exhibited that the EPS of *R. radiobacter* 36 can remove 2.15 g Na⁺ for 100 g EPS. Practical application should be based on considering this capacity of the EPS.

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